

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)
ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**STUDENTS' ATTITUDE TOWARD PHYSICS AS PREDICTORS OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE
IN POST-BASIC SCHOOL IN ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA**

Danladi, J. M.¹ & J. Adamu²

¹ & ²Department of Physical Sciences Education, Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: jimwaemamtso@gmail.com, 08031825041

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14908435>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated Students' Attitude toward Physics as Predictors of Academic Performance in Post-basic School in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions, two hypotheses. The study adopted a predictive correlation design. The population for the study comprises SSS III students offering physics at post-basic school (2023/2024 session) in Adamawa state totalling 16,220 within the 21 Local Government Areas and five education zones. The sample size of 390 SS III students were selected using Taro Yamane's formula and respondents selected using multi-stage technique. The instrument for data collection was Physics Students' Attitude Factors (PSAF) adapted from Attitudinal Scale for Senior Secondary Students' Attitude to Physics which is made up of 16 items. Physics Academic Performance Proforma (PAPP) was also used for collection of student's academic performance (2022/2023). The PSAFS was trial tested and subjected to reliability test using Cronbach Alpha statistical tool and yielded overall reliability index of 0.77. The data for the study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics specifically mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions one to two. While linear regression was used to test hypotheses one to two at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that (i) peer influence significantly predicted students' academic performance in physics in Post-Basic schools in Adamawa State. (ii) Physics teacher characteristics significantly predicted academic performance in Physics in Post-Basic schools in Adamawa state. The study recommended that Adamawa State Government should implement peer mentoring programs. Also, Adamawa state Government should invest in continuous professional development for physics teachers, focusing on enhancing their content knowledge.

Keywords: Peer Influence, Physics Teacher Characteristics, Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

Countries worldwide continue to invest in education to improve living standards. This commitment includes enhancing infrastructure, teacher training, curriculum development, and professional development opportunities. Quality education is a key driver of economic growth, as highlighted by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2023). Education equips learners with essential knowledge, fosters innovation, and encourages problem-solving through science and technology (Al-Shuaibi, 2014).

Science education is crucial to national development, with physics playing a significant role in expanding knowledge and technological progress. According to Wood (2020), scientific knowledge is acquired through experimentation and data collection, which contribute to national advancement Emmanuel *et al.* (2017). Physics seeks to understand natural phenomena

through observation, experimentation, and mathematical analysis. The Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NUST, 2016) emphasizes that physics aims to uncover quantitative physical laws governing the universe. Usman and Abubakar (2019) describe physics as the foundation of science and technology, providing essential knowledge for understanding natural laws and principles.

Many students struggle with physics, particularly in post-basic schools in Adamawa State (Godwin & Okoronka, 2015). Poor performance in physics has been linked to multiple factors, including school-based, teacher-related, societal, cultural, and student-related issues (Kavua, Adan, & Thinguri, 2015; Al-Muslimawi & Hamid, 2019; Al-Husaini & Shukor, 2022). Persistent underperformance in physics has serious consequences, such as students failing to meet university admission requirements for science-related fields, potentially hindering technological and educational progress.

A key factor affecting performance is students' negative attitudes toward physics, especially regarding laboratory practicals. Many students perceive physics as a difficult subject meant only for exceptionally talented individuals, discouraging engagement and leading to poor performance. Addressing these attitudes is critical for improving academic outcomes. Research indicates that attitude significantly influences learning, shaping students' willingness to engage with the subject (Agir, 2019). Assem, Nartey, Appiah, and Aidoo (2023) define academic attitude as a combination of emotions, thoughts, and behaviours toward a subject, which influences students' participation and interest in learning.

Several factors shape students' attitudes toward physics, including peer influence and teacher characteristics. These factors have been identified as significant contributors to academic performance (Zoker, Karim, & Bangura, 2022; Korur, 2022; Smith, Hong, Hsu, & Yan Lu, 2021; Putra *et al.*, 2020; Gurler & Baykara, 2020; Darmaji *et al.*, 2019; Maison *et al.*, 2019; Kaur & Zhao, 2017). Peer influence plays a crucial role in shaping students' behaviours and attitudes. Students tend to adopt the behaviours and norms of their peers, which can have positive or negative effects on academic performance (Olaleru & Owolabi, 2021). Oyeboade (2017) defines peer influence as the pressure exerted by peers to conform to group norms. Positive peer influence, such as encouragement and study collaboration, has been linked to improved physics performance (Huang, Wang, & Jia, 2017). Conversely, negative peer influence can lead to distractions and poor attitudes toward learning physics (Zhou & He, 2019). Educators and parents must guide students to engage in positive peer interactions that enhance their academic success.

Teacher characteristics also significantly impact students' attitudes and performance in physics. Teachers serve as role models, and their enthusiasm, teaching methods, and communication skills influence students' engagement with the subject. Approachable teachers who encourage participation and foster a growth mindset positively shape students' attitudes toward physics. Research supports that teacher characteristics strongly impact learner outcomes, with effective teaching playing a key role in academic performance (Coenen *et al.*, 2018). This study focuses on peer influence and teacher characteristics as key factors shaping students' attitudes toward physics.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Despite the importance of physics and its relevance to real-world applications, many students struggle to understand it and achieve good grades. The poor academic performance of post-basic school students in Adamawa State is concerning, as evidenced by research conducted by Godwin and Okoronka (2015). Over the years, more than 40% of post-basic school students in Adamawa State have consistently failed physics. This persistent failure has significant consequences for educational and scientific progress. A major concern is the inability of many students to meet university admission requirements for medicine and other science-related fields, potentially leading to a decline in science enrolment at both basic

and post-basic levels. This, in turn, may hinder technological and educational advancement, posing a challenge for parents, the government, and other stakeholders. One likely factor contributing to this failure is students' negative attitudes toward physics, particularly during laboratory practicals. Many students perceive physics as a difficult subject meant only for exceptionally talented individuals, discouraging engagement and fostering poor academic performance. Addressing these challenges is essential. Can a shift in students' attitudes toward physics improve academic performance and promote greater scientific advancement in post-basic schools in Adamawa State?

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study was to determine students' attitude towards Physics as predictors of their Academic performance in post-basic schools in Adamawa state, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine if:

1. Peer influence predicts students' academic performance in physics in post-basic schools in Adamawa state.
2. Physics teacher characteristics predict students' academic performance in physics in post-basic schools in Adamawa state.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the level of peer influence on students' academic performance in physics at post-basic schools in Adamawa state?
2. What is the level of influence of physics teacher characteristics on students' academic performance in physics in post-basic schools in Adamawa state?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: Peer influence does not significantly predict academic performance of students in physics in post-basic schools in Adamawa state.

H₀₂: Physics teacher characteristics do not significantly predict academic performance of students in physics in post-basic schools in Adamawa state.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study was grounded in Congruity Theory, developed by Jack Brehm (1956), which explores the relationship between attitudes and behaviours, emphasizing the importance of maintaining consistency between them. The theory posits that individuals strive to reduce cognitive dissonance, a psychological discomfort that arises from holding conflicting beliefs or engaging in contradictory actions by aligning their attitudes and behaviours. The study conceptualizes student's attitude factors toward physics as a predictor of academic performance.

Students' Attitude Factors: Refers to peer influence, Physics teacher characteristics at post-basic schools in Adamawa State.

Physics Academic Performance: This is the average score of SS II students offering physics during first, second and third terms examination at post-basic schools in Adamawa State. Research by Lawrence (2021) highlights the role of peer influence in shaping student behaviour, either positively or negatively. This study emphasizes the impact of teachers on students' attitudes toward learning, underscoring the importance of teacher characteristics in fostering student engagement. Similarly, Dan (2022) argues that a teacher's style, attitude, and behaviour significantly influence students' classroom participation and learning outcomes. Shikalepo (2019) identifies three key characteristics of an effective teacher: professional, personality, and

social attributes. These traits contribute to the quality of physics instruction, with effective teachers fostering student interest and reducing anxiety.

Tadese, Yeshaneh, and Mulu (2022) define academic performance as the extent to which students, teachers, or institutions attain their educational goals, commonly measured through continuous assessments or cumulative grade point averages. Ampofo and Osei-Owusu (2021) highlight various metrics used in academic performance evaluation, including standardized test scores, teacher ratings, and cognitive assessments. A study by Senyamator *et al.*, (2023) in Ghana examined the role of academic performance and peer influence in students' program choices. The study used a descriptive survey design, employing systematic sampling techniques. In contrast, the current study utilizes a correlational predictive design with a multi-stage sampling technique, focusing on students in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The previous studies have examined the impact of peer influence, and teacher characteristics on student performance, there is a lack of research that specifically predicts how students' attitudes toward physics determine their academic performance. Most prior studies have used descriptive or experimental designs rather than predictive correlational analysis. Many empirical studies have been conducted in different educational settings, such as senior high schools in Ghana. These studies do not account for the unique socio-cultural and educational dynamics of Nigerian post-basic schools, especially in Adamawa State. Also, research has established that peer influence and physics teacher characteristics affects academic performance, but do not explicitly investigate whether students' attitude toward physics predicted their academic performance in physics in post-basic school in Adamawa State. Post-basic schools in Nigeria cater to students who have completed basic education (junior secondary) and are preparing for advanced studies. This population is unique because, it represents a transitional stage where students solidify subject preferences and career pathways. By addressing these gaps, the study aims to provide insights that can inform policies and teaching strategies to improve physics performance at the post-basic school.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted predictive correlational research design. The study was carried out in post-basic schools in Adamawa state. The target population for this study is 16,220 SSS III students offering physics in post-basic schools in five education zones in Adamawa state, Nigeria. The sample of the study consisted of 390 SSS III students offering physics in post-basic schools in five education zones in Adamawa state (2022/2023) academic session. The study used questionnaire tagged "Physics Students' Attitude Factors (PSAF) and Physics Academic Performance Proforma (PAPP)" for data collection. The instrument consists of key: Very High Level (VHL) =5, High Level (HL) = 4, Moderate Level (ML) = 3, Low Level (LL) = 2, and Very Low Level (VLL) = 1 and Physics Students' Attitude Factors (PSAF) covering 1-7 items under peer influence, 8-16 items under physics teacher characteristics. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions. To interpret the mean values, the following criteria was established: mean values between 4.50 and 5.00 indicated a very high level, mean values between 3.50 and 4.49 indicated a high level, mean values between 2.50 and 3.49 indicated a moderate level, mean values between 1.50 and 2.49 indicated a low level, and mean values between 0.50 and 1.49 indicated a very low level. Descriptive and inferential statistics was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What is the level of peer influence on students' academic performance in physics at post-basic schools in Adamawa state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Peer Influence on Students’ Academic Performance in Physics in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State?

SN	Items (n=390)	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	My friends encourage me to learn physics because it is fun with them.	3.51	1.64	HL
2	I have good feelings toward physics because my friends discuss challenging topics together	2.94	1.59	ML
3	I really like physics because my friends celebrate good performance in grades	2.92	1.60	ML
4	My friends and I should learn about physics because of its importance to society	3.71	1.51	HL
5	My best friend like physics	2.94	1.66	ML
6	My friends like physics due to its real-world applications	3.35	1.53	ML
7	Most of my friends do well in physics	2.65	1.54	ML
Grand Mean		3.15	1.74	ML

Table 1 showed that the means for items 1 and 4 are at high level while the other items are within the true limit 2.50-3.49 (Moderate Level). The result as indicated by the grand mean of 3.15 and standard deviation of 1.74 revealed that peer influence on students’ academic performance in physics at Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State is at a moderate level.

Research Question 2: What is the level of influence of physics teacher characteristics on students’ academic performance in physics in post-basic schools in Adamawa state?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of influence of Physics Teacher Characteristics on Students’ Academic Performance in Physics in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State

SN	Items (n=390)	Mean	S. D	Remark
8	I feel nervous in physics class anytime I see my physics teacher	3.40	1.63	ML
9	I usually look forward to my physics class because of my physics teacher dressing	2.90	1.58	ML
10	Our physics laboratory is attractive because the physics teachers are neat	3.09	1.68	ML
11	Our physics laboratory contains interesting equipment due to efforts of my physics teacher	2.68	1.60	ML
12	My physics teacher encourages me to learn more Physics	2.94	1.58	ML
13	I enjoy talking to my physics teacher about any problem I have in physics	2.78	1.58	ML
14	My physics teacher makes me to develop interest in physics with regards to physics practical	2.60	1.42	ML
15	My physics teacher encourages me to make good grades in physics after exams	2.96	1.35	ML
16	I like physics as a result of my teacher’s encouragement	2.86	1.33	ML
Grand Mean		2.91	1.53	ML

Table 2 showed that the means for all the items are within the true limit 2.50- 3.49 (Moderate Level). The result as indicated by the grand mean of 2.91 and standard deviation of 1.53 revealed that physics teacher characteristics’ influence on students’ academic performance in physics at Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State is at a moderate level.

Hypotheses testing

HO₁: Peer influence does not significantly predict academic performance of students in physics at post-basic schools in Adamawa state.

Table 3a: Summary of ANOVA of Linear Regression for Peer Influence and Academic Performance of Students in Physics in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.768	1	.768	7.824	.005 ^b
	Residual	38.096	388	.098		
	Total	38.864	389			

- a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Peer Influence

The result in Table 3a revealed that peer influence significantly predicted academic performance with $F_{(1, 388)} = 445.274, p < 0.05$. Since the computed p-value (0.005) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded that peer influence made a significant prediction to academic performance of students in Physics at Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

Table 3b: Model Summary of Linear Regression for Peer Influence and Academic Performance of Students in Physics in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.141 ^a	.020	.017	.31334

- a. Predictors: (Constant), PI

The result in Tables 3b indicated a model summary of how the independent variable explained the variance in the dependent variable. The result showed there is a very weak but positive relationship between peer influence and students' academic performance in Physics with $R = 0.141$ and the adjusted R-square value (.017) indicated that 1.7% of academic performance in this study can be explained by peer influence.

Table 3c: Beta Coefficients of Linear Regression for Peer Influence and Academic Performance of Students in Physics in Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.115	.048		86.090	.000
	PI	-.040	.014	.141	-2.797	.005

- a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance

The result in Table 3c revealed the Beta coefficient of regression analysis. It revealed that the independent variable, peer influence explained 14.1% variability in the outcome variable, academic performance of students in Physics at Post Basic Schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. This indicated that peer influence made a minimal contribution to academic performance.

HO₂: Physics teacher characteristics do not significantly predict academic performance of students in physics at post-basic schools in Adamawa state

Table 4a: Summary of ANOVA results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Physics Teachers' Characteristics Skills and Academic Performance in Physics

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.572	1	.572	5.796	.017 ^b
	Residual	38.292	388	.099		
	Total	38.864	389			

- a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' characteristics

The result in Table 4a showed that peer influence significantly predicted academic performance with $F_{(1, 388)} = 5.796, p < 0.05$. Since the computed p-value (0.017) is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected and concluded Physics teachers' characteristics made significant prediction of academic performance of students in Physics at Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa state.

Table 4b: Model Summary results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Physics Teachers' Characteristics and Academic Performance in Physics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.121 ^a	.015	.012	.31415

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Physics teachers' characteristics

The result in Tables 7b indicated that there is a very weak but positive relationship between Physics teachers' characteristics and students' academic performance in Physics with $R=0.121$ and the adjusted R-square value (.012) indicates that 1.2% of academic performance in this study could be explained by Physics teachers' characteristics and it indicated a model summary of how the independent variable explained the variance in the dependent variable.

Table 4c: Coefficient of Beta results from Regression Analysis of Prediction between Physics Teachers' Characteristics and Academic Performance in Physics

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	3.876	.049		78.340	.000
	PTC	.039	.016	.121	2.4t07	.017

- a. Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance

The result in Table 4c revealed the Beta coefficient of regression analysis. It revealed that the predictor variable, Physics teachers' characteristics explained 12.1% variability in the outcome variable, academic performance in Physics at

Post-Basic Schools in Adamawa State, Nigeria. This indicated that physics teachers' characteristics made a low contribution to academic performance.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The first finding of this study revealed that peer influence among students offering physics at post-basic schools in Adamawa state is moderate, and significantly predicts students' academic performance in physics at post-basic schools in Adamawa state. This agrees with the findings of Ikusika and Okoli (2023), Azua (2016). The findings of both studies revealed that there was a significant relationship between peer influence and academic achievement in students' scores. Moreover, Adeyemi, Bello, Uwaoma, Anwanane and Nwangburuka (2019) showed that peer group has significantly influence on academic performance of undergraduate students in Babcock University. Therefore, schools should develop programs to help support peer groups and promote academic excellence and educators should consider peer influence when designing strategies to improve academic performance, also encouraging positive peer relationships to enhance students' academic achievement.

The second finding of this study revealed that, physics teachers' characteristics is at moderate level. This showed that, it significantly predicted students' academic performance in physics at post-basic schools in Adamawa state. This concurred with the finding of Mbaka, Mwalw'a and Adhiambo (2022), Michael (2023). The findings of both studies revealed that there was significantly prediction between physics teacher characteristics in physics at public secondary schools and academic performance. However, Abraham (2020) showed that Physics teacher characteristics such as; academic attainment, teaching experience, teaching methods, utilization of teaching resources, attitude towards teaching Physics and learners' characteristics such as social-economic backgrounds, study habits, career aspirations and peer influences influence enrolment and academic performance in Physics. Similarly, with the finding of Keller, Neumann and Fischer (2016) who found that teacher pedagogical content knowledge predicts student performance through cognitive activation in Germany and Switzerland. Hence, educators and policymakers should prioritize teacher training and development. Physics teachers should focus on improving their pedagogical content knowledge and schools can implement strategies to enhance teacher effectiveness and student learning performance.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that students' attitude toward physics, including peer influence, physics teachers' characteristics significantly impact students' academic performance in physics in post-basic schools in Adamawa state, contributing 31.6% to their performance.

RECOMMENDATION

1. Adamawa state Government should implement peer mentoring programs where high-achieving students in physics can provide support and guidance to their peers.
2. Adamawa state Government should invest in continuous professional development for physics teachers, focusing on enhancing their personalities and content knowledge.

REFERENCES

- Abraham, K., S. (2020). Influence of teachers' and learners' characteristics on enrolment and academic performance in physics among secondary schools in Tharaka-nithi county, Kenya. PhD Thesis. Kenyatta university.
- Adeyemi, B., F. Bello, A., A. Uwaoma, C., O. & Bassey, B. (2019). Peer group influence on academic performance of undergraduate students in Badcock university. *African Educational Research Journal*, 7(2), 81-87

- Agir, M., S. (2019). Students' attitudes towards learning, a study on their academic achievement and internet addiction. *World Journal of Education*, 9(4), 103-111. doi: 10.5430/wje.v9n4p109
- Al Husaini, Y., N., S. & Shukor, S., A. (2022). Factors affecting students' academic performance: A review. *RES MILITARIS*, 12(6), 284-294.
- Al-Shuaibi, A. (2014). The importance of education. Salah college of technology. Retrieved at Research Gate. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260075970- The Importance of Education](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260075970-The_Importance_of_Education)
- Ampofo, E., T. & Osei-Owusu, B. (2021). Investigating students' academic performance as mediated by students' academic ambition and effort in the public senior high schools in Ashanti Mampong municipality of Ghana. *International Journal of Academic Research and Reflection*. 3(5), 19-35.
- Assem, H., D. Nartey, L. Appiah, E. & Aidoo, J., K. (2023). A Review of students' academic performance in physics: attitude, instructional methods, misconceptions and teachers qualification. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 4(1), 84-92.
- Azua, F.H. (2016). *Relationship between peer influence, parental support and academic achievement of secondary school students in Giwa Educational zone, Kaduna State*, ABU Zaria: Unpublished M.Ed Thesis.
- Brehm, J., W. (1956). Post-decision changes in the desirability of alternatives. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 52(3), 384-389.
- Coenen, J., Cornelisz, I., Groot, W., Maassen van den Brink, H., & Van Klaveren, C. (2018). Teacher characteristics and their effects on student test scores: a systematic review. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 32(3), 848-877.
- Dah, M. (2022). Students' perception of their physics teachers' classroom practices. *Asian Journal of Research and Reviews in Physics*. 6(2), 16-24
- Darmaji, D. Astalini, A. Kurniawan, D., A. Perdana, R. & Putra, D., S. (2019). A study relationship attitude toward physics, motivation, and character discipline students senior high school, *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*. 11(3), 99-109.
- Emmanuel, C., H. Emmanuel, A., T. Audu, G., K. & Macmillan, M., J. (2017). The role of physics in national development: A lesson for Nigeria. 110-114.
- Godwin, B., A. & Okoronka, A., U. (2015). Attitude and academic performance of senior secondary school students in physics in Nigeria. In *Proceedings of SOCIOINT15- 2nd International Conference on Education, Social Sciences and Humanities* Istanbul, Turkey .499-506.
- Gürler, S., A. & Baykara, O. (2020). Development of an attitude scale for physics courses and a review of student attitudes. *Journal of Baltic Science Education*, 19(1), 6-24 doi:10.33225/jbse/20.19.06
- Huang, Y. Wang, J. & Jia, J. (2017). Effects of peer feedback on the academic performance of physics students: A quasi-experimental study. *International Journal of Science Education*, 39(18), 2482-2499.
- Ikusika, B.A., & Okoli, J. N (2023). Peer influence as a predictor of upper basic education students' academic achievement in basic science in Enugu State. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)*, 10(10), 115-120.
- Kaur, D. & Zhao, Y. (2017). Development of physics attitude scale (PAS): An instrument to measure students' attitude toward physics, *Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 26(5), 291-304
- Kavua, G., M. Adan, M., A. & Thinguri, R. (2015). An Investigation into Factors that Influence the choice of physics by secondary school learners *Researchjournali's Journal of Education* (3)4 ISSN 2347-8225
- Keller, M., M. Neumann, K. & Fischer, H., E. (2016). The impact of physics teachers' pedagogical content knowledge and motivation on students' achievement and interest. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*. Doi:10.1002/tea.21378

- Korur, F. (2022). Attitude toward physics teaching of science teachers: A revised scale and analysis. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 12(1), 190-208
- Lawrence, K. (2021). The mediating role of social internet use on the correlation of parental efficacy, peer influence and social functioning of adolescents in the current era. *Current Research in Behavioural Science*, 2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crbeha.2021.100032>.
- Maison, Ernawati, M., D., W. Budiarti, R., S. Kurniawan, W. Tari, Y., N. Puspitasari, O. Jannah, N. & Putra, D., S. (2019). Learning in nature science: social implication, normality of scientist, attitudes towards investigation of natural science, and interest adds to science learning time. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research* 8(12), 1478-1484.
- Mbaka, N., K. Mwalwâ, S. & Adhiambo, J., M. (2022). Teacher characteristics and students' academic achievements in physics in stem model public secondary schools in Nairobi Metropolitan Kenya. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 6(02), 126-135.
- Michael, U. E. (2023). Teachers' characteristics and secondary school students' academic achievement in Physics. *Universal Academic Journal of Education, Science and Technology*, 5(1), 111-121.
- Norwegian university of science and technology (2016). Physics education. [https:// www.ntnu.edu/physics](https://www.ntnu.edu/physics)
- OECD (2023), education at a glance 2023: OECD Indicators, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/e13bef63-en>
- Olaleru, E., A & Owolabi, R., O. (2021). Peer influence and school library use by students in public secondary schools in Lagos state, Nigeria. Information impact. *Journal of Information and Knowledge Management*, 12(2), 87-101, DOI <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/ijikm.v12i2.7>
- Oyeboade, J., A. (2017). Socio-economic status, peer pressure and use of social media by undergraduate students in university of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 1495. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/1495>
- Putra, D., S. Irawan, A. Yanto, J., P. Putra, M., M. Adli, S. Dewi, U., P. & Nasih, N., R. (2020). Relationship of attitude with student learning environment toward physics. *Tarbiyah: Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan*, 9(2), 78-86.
- Senyamator, F. Abagbana, V., N. Nugba, R., M. Adu, A. & Asabere, M., A. (2023). The role of academic performance and peer influence in senior high school students' programme choice in Ghana. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 4(2), 66-83.
- Shikalepo, E., E. (2019). The three characteristics of an effective teacher. *Research Journal of Education*. 5(8), 151-160
- Smith, T., J. Hong, Z., R. Hsu, W., Y. & Lu, Y., Y. (2022). The relationship of sense of school belonging to physics attitude among high school students in advanced physics courses. *Science Education*, 106(4), 830-851.
- Tadese, M. Yeshaneh, A. & Mulu, G., B. (2022). Determinants of good academic performance among university students in Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Medical Education*, 22(1), 395.
- Usman, I. S. & Abubakar, Y. B. (2019). Senior secondary school Physics curriculum content coverage and student's achievement in Katagum educational zone, Bauchi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 12(4), 489-499.
- Wood, D. (2020). Three branches of natural science physical, earth & life. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/three-branches-of-natural-science-physical-earth-life.html>.
- Zhou, Y., & He, M. (2019). Peer relationships and academic achievement: evidence from middle and high school students in China. *PloS one*, 14(11), e0225035.
- Zoker, M., E. Karim, S. & Bangura, S., R. (2022). The impact of physics practical on the teaching and learning methodology of senior secondary schools in Sierra Leone. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 3(3), 458-458.